

Isothermal crystallization modelling of PEKK composites: kinetic and morphology predictions

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Massive use of composites in aero-structures

Digital material modelling for virtual testing

High-performance semi-crystalline Thermoplastic Prepreg (PEKK, PEEK)

Representative Volume Element (RVE)

Fibre and Matrix Properties

Interface / Interphase Properties

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Crystallinity and matrix morphology

High-performance **semi-crystalline** Thermoplastic Prepreg (PEKK, PEEK)

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High-performance semi-crystalline Thermoplastic Prepreg (PEKK, PEEK)

Matrix properties depend on crystallinity

T. Choupin et al. 21st ICCM, Xi'an, 2017

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Matrix properties depend on crystallinity

Carbon fibres influence the crystallization behaviour

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Matrix properties depend on crystallinity

Carbon fibres influence the crystallization behaviour

Fillers used for lightning protection can also affect the crystallization behaviour

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Crystallinity and matrix morphology

PEKK 7003 (70/30 T/I copolymers)

High-performance semi-crystalline Thermoplastic Prepreg (PEKK, PEEK)

- 1 - **Characterization** of the crystallization kinetics by DSC and using a hot stage under microscope
- 2 - Crystallization **kinetics modelling** considering primary and secondary crystallization mechanisms
- 3 - Crystallization **simulation**
- 4 - **Effect of fillers** on kinetics and morphology

Isothermal Crystallization procedure

DSC Perkin Elmer 8500

Linkam THMS600 Hot Stage

DSC : Characterization of crystallization kinetics through the exotherm of the phase change

DSC Perkin Elmer 8500

Derivation + Normalization

DSC : Characterization of crystallization kinetics through the exotherm of the phase change

DSC Perkin Elmer 8500

Hot Stage : Crystallization characterization through morphology : spherulite nucleation and growth

Linkam THMS600 Hot Stage

PEKK 7002 Isothermal crystallization at 315°C followed by a cooling step at 20°C/min

DSC

DSC Perkin Elmer 8500

Non-symmetrical sigmoidal shape

Hot Stage

Linkam THMS600 Hot Stage

Symmetrical sigmoidal shape consistent with Avrami description

Different crystallization time in DSC and Hot Stage

Non-symmetrical sigmoidal shape

Symmetrical sigmoidal shape consistent with Avrami description

Crystallization kinetics modelling requires the use of a specific model accounting for the contribution of each mechanism

Spherulitic morphology is only related to primary crystallization

Crystallization kinetics modelling requires the use of a specific model accounting for the contribution of each mechanism

Spherulitic morphology is only related to primary crystallization

Use of Hillier's formulation but considering a n^{th} order secondary crystallization mechanism

$$\alpha(t) = \omega_1 \alpha_1(t) + \omega_2 \underbrace{\int_0^t \alpha_1(t) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(1 - \exp\left(-K_2(t-\theta)^{n_2}\right) \right) d\theta}_{\alpha_2(t)}$$

$\alpha_1(t)$ assumed only related to spherulite nucleation (N) and growth (G) rates, and considering a 3D growth

$$\alpha_1(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\pi}{3} N G^3 t^3\right)$$

Growth rate measured by monitoring the diameter of several spherulites

Linkam THMS600 Hot Stage

Growth rate measured by monitoring the diameter of several spherulites

Nucleation rate measured by numbering the nuclei on binarized images

Growth rate measured by monitoring the diameter of several spherulites

Nucleation rate measured by numbering the nuclei on binarized images

MODEL FORMULATION

$$\alpha(t) = w_1\alpha_1(t) + w_2\alpha_2(t)$$

$$\alpha_1(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\pi}{3}NG^3t^3\right) \quad \alpha_2(t) = \int_0^t 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\pi}{3}NG^3\theta^3\right) \frac{d}{dt} \left(1 - \exp(-K_2(t - \theta)^{n2})\right) d\theta$$

Growth rate

Hoffman-Weeks model

$$G = G_0 \exp\left(-\frac{U^*}{R(T - T_\infty)}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{K_g}{T\Delta T}\right)$$

Nucleation rate

Koscher and Fulchiron model

$$\ln(N) = a\Delta T + b$$

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$$\alpha(t) = w_1\alpha_1(t) + w_2\alpha_2(t)$$

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Comparison of experimental data (Hot Stage) with the direct simulation of primary crystallization

MODEL FORMULATION

$\alpha(t) = w_1\alpha_1(t) + w_2\alpha_2(t)$

$\alpha_1(t) = 1 - \exp(-\frac{\pi}{3}NG^3t^3)$ $\alpha_2(t) = \int_0^t 1 - \exp(-\frac{\pi}{3}NG^3\theta^3) \frac{d}{dt} (1 - \exp(-K_2(t - \theta)^{n_2})) d\theta$

Experimental Data (DSC)

Good agreement with experimental data after w_1 , K_2 and n_2 identification by inverse analysis

MODEL FORMULATION

■ $\alpha(t) = w_1\alpha_1(t) + w_2\alpha_2(t)$

■ $\alpha_1(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\pi}{3}NG^3t^3\right)$ ■ $\alpha_2(t) = \int_0^t 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\pi}{3}NG^3\theta^3\right) \frac{d}{dt} \left(1 - \exp(-K_2(t - \theta)^{n2})\right) d\theta$

Simulation of spherulite growth (primary crystallization) using the pixel coloring method

Algorithm main steps (instantaneous nucleation) :

- random distribution of nucleus regarding the nucleation rate N
- Identification of the distance between nucleus (Voronoi cells)
- Determination of spherulites radius at any time according to the growth rate G

→ Morphological parameters can be extracted

→ The morphology can be exported for mechanical analysis

DSC analysis of PEKK crystallization kinetics with increasing fraction of carbon fibres

Faster PEKK crystallization with the increase of fibre fraction

PEKK crystallisation in Hot Stage in presence of two carbon fibres

Apparition of a trans-crystalline region around the fibres but of same growth rate as the surrounding spherulites

→ Nucleation on carbon fibre surfaces significantly affects crystallization kinetics

→ The effect of the trans-crystalline structure on the secondary crystallization still needs to be investigated

Pixel coloring method extended in 3D for the study of representative structures

Application of the method to real composite microstructures (reconstructed from tomography measurements)

- Complementary techniques were used to characterize PEKK crystallization kinetics (DSC and hot stage under microscope)
 - Contributions of primary and secondary crystallization mechanisms on the total crystallization process were identified
- The Hillier formulation was used for modelling PEKK crystallization kinetics
 - Coupled equation accounting for the interaction of primary and secondary crystallization kinetics
 - Limited number of parameters were numerically identified
 - Avrami equation successfully predicts primary crystallization
 - Simulation of primary crystallization using the pixel coloring method
- Influence of carbon fibres on PEKK crystallization were investigated
 - The higher is the fibre fraction, the faster is crystallization
 - Primary crystallization (trancrystalline and spherulitic phases) can explain the faster crystallization
 - Nucleation density increases in the presence of carbon fibres but the growth rate is not affected
- Prospects
 - Effect of nanowires on crystallization ?
 - Effect of trans-crystallinity on secondary crystallization kinetics
 - Effect of morphology on the mechanical behaviour (simulation-Experimental)